

Some Problems Arising in Teaching English

Bakhodirov Ulugbek Bakhodir ugli

Department of the integrated English language course -3, English language faculty-3, Uzbekistan state university of world languages

Article information:

Manuscript received: 01 Dec 2025; **Accepted:** 02 Jan 2025; **Published:** 07 Feb 2025

Abstract: The article discusses the improvement of speech skills and abilities, the development of a way to effectively learn English. The purpose of the study is to identify difficulties in learning a foreign language. To study the behavior and ability, age and psychological climate of each student. To find out what prevents the child from effectively learning a foreign language.

Keys words: learning difficulties, improving speech skills, age and psychological climate, effectively learning a foreign language, problems in learning.

At any time, at any age, the great goal of mankind is to educate a conscious, educated generation. As for our country in the new century, its current society is multinational, multilingual and multicultural. Therefore, one of the most pressing issues is the formation of a multicultural personality with multilingual knowledge, adapted to such a multilingual society.

In this study, we used the methods of description, observation and analysis. Reading the works of world researchers, comparing the methods used in teaching English in our country, we offer several ways to overcome barriers in teaching English through comparative research. Language teaching is one of the most sought-after professions. With the appropriate education and work experience, a teacher gets the opportunity to demonstrate their teaching skills, immerse themselves in an exciting culture, meet new people from all over the world and travel to countries you have never visited. As in any teaching job, teaching English as a second language is not without its challenges [3].

We fully agree with this opinion; English language leads any student to a wonderful world and has many advantages for self-improvement, acquaintance with the values of another country. There are many difficulties in teaching English, which has become a world language. However, any teacher who finds the key to these problems thinks about the best ways to learn a foreign language and can eliminate any obstacles using effective, advanced technologies. A scientist from Europe Liton (2016) noted in his study that both teachers and students face problems in learning English. The problems of teachers and students are poor knowledge of English. Students face problems related to the lack of motivation in learning English [2, p. 93].

Teaching English at the secondary school level is naturally very different from teaching the language at special and higher levels of education such as college or university. The difference can be found in numerous components of teaching, including the curriculum, the learning environment, the students, and the teaching or delivery of content [3, p. 81]. Since the teaching materials are simple in primary school, many people may think that the content of this education is more accessible for children to master. However, teaching English to primary school children is fraught with difficulties, since primary school students are young children who have not yet learned to take responsibility for their tasks compared to high school students and students in colleges and universities. Teaching a foreign language at school

requires a high level of professional skill, love for children, as well as effort and skill in presenting the material so that students successfully learn it and show interest in the subject. This, of course, can be achieved with some effort, and, as practice shows, success depends not so much on experience as on the enthusiasm, energy and interest of the teacher [2, p. 62]. We would like to note that the obstacles that arise in the process of teaching English can be explained by the fact that students do not pay full attention to the lesson material, quickly get tired during the lesson, lose concentration during the lesson and in most cases do not show interest in the lesson explained.

The problems found vary depending on how they relate to students, teachers and the learning process. On the students' side, the results of the study showed that problems in learning English also arise from the students themselves. These problems include students' insufficient mastery of vocabulary, low concentration, lack of parental support, lack of discipline and speech problems [1, p. 55]. We would like to add to this opinion that the increase in the number of English teachers from year to year does not help to remove barriers to students' effective learning of English. Such obstacles can only be prevented through creative research and the use of new technologies.

When teaching English, we, as foreign language teachers, face a number of difficulties. Unreasonably developed textbooks, which, on the one hand, cover the same topics, but, on the other hand, are overloaded with grammar that is not explained at the proper level, overloaded with unnecessary vocabulary for children, tasks are too complicated, and the texts are written in a far from modern language adapted for children, present only minor difficulty [3, p. 371]. According to this point of view, the language of school textbooks is really difficult. It would be useful for students to receive a quality education if the textbooks developed tasks that would be understandable, simple and meet their interests. The reason for this is as follows: in order to cover all the educational materials in the curriculum, the teacher can lose students' interest in the English language, forcing students to perform complex, difficult language tasks. Nowadays, new information technologies have been introduced in English. It is very effective to use it as a means of increasing interest in the language. New teaching technologies are currently used in schools. Since the content of education and its requirements are changing, it is almost impossible to achieve an increase in the quality of education without such a requirement. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce innovations, that is, to increase the activity of schoolchildren based on the innovative system, self-confidence, development of cognitive creativity, to determine the qualities of their activity - confidence in diagnostic methods, teach them to freely express themselves in class and outside the classroom. This helps to determine the norms, signs, indicators of innovative behavior. Most studies confirm that the use of ICT in education helps students play an active role in the learning process instead of being traditional passive students [3, p. 59].

Lack of motivation among students can be caused by lack of support from their parents. Mumary Songbatumis detailed her experience when she once caught a student who did not bring any books to school due to forgetfulness. In contrast, other students intentionally left their books on the table in the classroom. Mumary Songbatumis believes that such things would not have happened if the students' parents supervised their children's learning at home [1, p. 65]. Unfortunately, we also have such problems in our country. Here we would like to note that the problems of teachers in teaching English to students are closely related to the responsibilities of parents. The biggest problems are in teaching the class with the help of books. Many teachers do not understand how to effectively use new textbooks. Teachers do not understand the fundamental principles of textbooks and use traditional ways [1, p. 64]. This is directly related to the general written and oral speech in the formation of reading skills in schoolchildren. Teaching a foreign language is based on a functional system. Therefore, it is important to consider the conditions of use of the language taught in the environment. To learn a foreign language, it is necessary to use the most innovative methods and traditional teaching aids.

The basis of a teacher's skills is the level of vocabulary, or more precisely, the level of vocabulary and speech culture that we need to organize our thoughts. To do this, the teacher must first teach in a language that he or she is fluent in. The second condition is that teaching must be in a language that is

understandable. Therefore, we must always be guided by the fact that teaching in a language that is understandable is the principle of professional development.

Interest in innovation is the main internal desire. Students are interested in something new and unknown. Such activities mobilize the entire mind, inner strength and energy of the student. Therefore, interest is an important factor in the education of both well-educated and well-developed people. "Does knowledge obtained through involuntary persuasion and coercion give rise to a developed mind?" - say scientists. Therefore, learning must be in a state of fundamental voluntary interest. In this regard, English teachers use the best world practices and new technological methods in language teaching to improve the quality of English language teaching. The main idea of the article under consideration is to allow students to develop in a certain direction as a holistic system, the purpose of which is to teach these technological methods; personality-oriented education; from explanation to understanding; from monologue to dialogue; from social control to development; aimed at the transition from management to self-management.

And the main task of the teacher is communication, opening the way for interaction of students, giving them creative freedom. Therefore, the main goal is to use new information technologies in education in the country. This is a technical tool, new information and communication technologies and a new system of teaching methods in the education system. One of the main materials in English that schoolchildren study is a list of words with their vocabularies of meanings, known as a dictionary (Brown and Hatch, 1995). Vocabulary learning can be manifested in the study of simple objects such as objects around us, names of fruits, animals, sports, games and giving instructions. This may not be easy because most students are learning English for the first time [1, p. 56]. Indeed, as Brown and Hatch say, when learning any foreign language, the first thing that matters is having a sufficient vocabulary. It is not an easy task to raise the level of a student who is learning English for the first time and speaks a foreign language fluently.

In this study, we tried to find answers to the following questions:

- ✓ What barriers do teachers face in the classroom when teaching a foreign language?
- ✓ What barriers do teachers face outside the classroom when teaching a foreign language?
- ✓ What barriers do students face when learning a foreign language?

In our analysis, we identified the following barriers in teaching English.

Shyness. The first obstacle to learning a foreign language is shyness. Students who are just starting to learn a foreign language will be afraid: "I will not be able to speak this language correctly, I will not be able to learn this language." For this reason, students develop self-doubt and shyness. For example, there may be some shy students who, despite doing their homework, do not feel comfortable talking to their classmates. This is one of the main obstacles for students to be fluent in English.

Lack of time. One of the main obstacles to learning English is the lack of time. No matter how well organized and effective the lesson is, if the student does not apply what he has learned in practice, he will quickly forget what he has learned during the lesson. Therefore, it is good to have enough time for the student to develop his English skills.

Inadequacy of the textbook. It is not enough to provide the student with a textbook in English lessons. It is also important to provide them with dictionaries, picture dictionaries, teaching materials, worksheets. Only if students are equipped with all the learning materials, they will have enough opportunities to learn a foreign language quickly and effectively.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, we would like to note that there are many barriers in teaching a foreign language, from technical problems to student motivation. Our study has shown that motivation is necessary to overcome most of the difficulties in learning a foreign language. In addition, the use of ICT in teaching foreign

languages plays an important role. Student shyness, lack of time, textbooks with difficult tasks, etc. - it was found that such problems have a negative impact on the level of student English proficiency. In solving these problems, it was found that barriers are eliminated only when the language teaching methods win the interest of students, using effective new technologies in language teaching. The results of this study will be of great help to English teachers in all secondary schools. In addition, using the proposed barriers to English language teaching in this study will help students to be better at English in the future.

In general, in order to overcome the barriers that students face when teaching English, the teacher must constantly improve his or her professional skills. Moreover, as we have seen in our study, it is the teacher who must overcome the negative habits that any student has when learning a language. Today, as we have already mentioned, we have highlighted some elements of eliminating the barriers that we face when teaching a foreign language. However, this study will continue in the future, completely eliminating barriers to teaching English and demonstrating effective work. This is due to the fact that barriers to learning English are one of the most pressing problems in the direction of high-quality learning of this language. Based on the data provided in the study, it became clear that it is necessary to eliminate barriers in teaching English, and in the course of such elimination it is necessary to work intensively, always demonstrating the skills of the teacher.

Bibliography

1. Chaney A.L., Burk T.L. Teaching Oral Communication in Grades k-8. Boston: Allyn and Bacon, 1998.
2. Kainz F. Psychologie der Sprache: in 4 Bd. Stuttgart, 1951.
3. Meirbekov A.K., Begaidarova A.E. Problems faced by teachers when teaching English in secondary schools // Modern science-intensive technologies. - 2021. - No. 9. - P. 204-210.
4. Bakirova H.B. Methodology of Lexical Competence Formation of Power-Engineering Students based on CBA and its Experimental Research in Teaching ESP. Pubmedia Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris. – Indonesia. 2024. – №2,1.
5. Bakirova X.B. Terminological competence as the basis of professional readiness of a future specialist. “Tarjimashunoslik: muammolar, yechimlar va istiqbollari” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman, 1(1), 514–517.
6. Samigova X., Guo T. Chjao Y. Dialogic rhetoric of English and Uzbek. Translation studies: problems, solutions and prospects, 2022. -Pp. 304–307.